

Service-Oriented Enterprise Architecture (SoEA) Adoption and Maturity Measurement Model: A Systematic Review

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Abstract : This article provides a systematic review of existing research related to the Service-oriented Enterprise Architecture (SoEA) adoption and maturity measurement model. The review's main goals are to support research, to facilitate other researcher's search for relevant studies and to propose areas for future studies within this area. In addition, this article provides useful information on SoEA adoption issues and its related maturity model, based on research-based knowledge. The review results suggest that motives, critical success factors (CSFs), implementation status and benefits are the most frequently studied areas and that each of these areas would benefit from further exposure.

Keywords : systematic literature review, service-oriented architecture, adoption, maturity model

Conference Title : ICCSSE 2014 : International Conference on Computer Science and Software Engineering

Conference Location : Penang, Malaysia

Conference Dates : December 16-17, 2014